

Wikimedia Commons data model for Natural History specimen images

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[Photograph of *Anisoplaca achyrota* NZAC04201756.](#)
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Scope

This Structured Data on Commons (SDC) data model is intended to apply to natural history specimen media files as digitised by natural history institutions and others and added to Wikimedia Commons. Where appropriate, this documentation attempts to map Wikidata properties used to add SDC to media files to the equivalent Darwin Core data standard (<https://dwc.tdwg.org/>) term.

Motivation

The main purpose of SDC is to add data about the **media file** to the file itself. SDC improves access, searchability, exploration and provides new ways to use content held on Wikimedia Commons. This is also the case for files related to natural history specimens.

However, where a natural history specimen depicted in the file does not have its own Wikidata item (i.e. the specimen is **not** a type specimen), there is often data related to the specimen that, if added to the file as structured data, supports a wider range of Wikimedia Commons queries.

Adding SDC relating to the specimen itself to the file that depicts that object can improve the ability of third parties to find relevant natural history content, can assist with connecting knowledge from different sources, gives context to the file as well as the specimen depicted in it, and improves end user ability to explore natural history collections and topics on multiple platforms.

Where data related to the natural history specimen depicted in file is added to Wikimedia Commons, this model recommends the addition of the qualifier [applies to part](#) (P518) → [physical object](#) (Q223557). The addition of this qualifier highlights that such structured data statements relate to the specimen depicted rather than the media file itself.

If the specimen depicted is a [type specimen](#) it is best practice to create a Wikidata item for that specimen and add data to that item in line with the [data model for type specimen Wikidata items](#). The holotype specimen Wikidata item can be linked to the specimen image via a “depicts” ([P180](#)) statement.

We have attempted to draft this model with the end user and their potential queries in mind. Examples of the types of Wikimedia Commons queries we considered were:

- Show all photographs of a particular species. For example “Asaphodes ida”
- Show all photographs of holotype specimens held in the New Zealand Arthropod Collection
- Show all files depicting holotype specimens in the genus Asaphodes
- Show all photographs of species collected at Ida Mountain
- Show all files depicting male moths collected by George Vernon Hudson
- Show all photographs of holotype specimens digitized by the Auckland Museum
- Show all files of species collected in the April at the Otari-Wilton’s Bush
- Show all files for which the Challenger Expedition is a significant event
- Show all files of larvae images of endemic to New Zealand moth specimens

Summary of minimum data model for specimen images

Properties related to data about the file:

Depicts ([P180](#))
 Copyright status ([P6216](#))
 Copyright licence ([P275](#))
 Inception ([P571](#))
 Collection ([P195](#))
 Instance of ([P31](#))
 Creator ([P170](#))
 Source of file ([P7482](#))
 Sponsor ([P859](#))
 Copyright holder ([P3931](#))

Properties related to data about the physical object depicted:

Inventory number ([P217](#))
 Collection date ([P14027](#))
 Collector ([P13914](#))
 Specimen classifier ([P14026](#))
 Location collected ([P14117](#))
 Coordinate location ([P625](#))
 Sex or gender ([P21](#))
 Significant event ([P793](#))
 Biological phase ([P4774](#))

All statements added using properties related to data about the physical object depicted are required to have the qualifier

[applies to part](#) (P518) → [physical object](#) (Q223557)

Whether to add to a specimen image file the structured data relating to the physical object depicted will depend on whether the specimen depicted is a type specimen and has an existing Wikidata item.

If a specimen image file relates to a type specimen and that file has a “depicts” statement linking it to a type specimen Wikidata item, the properties related to data about the physical object depicted should **NOT be added** to the image file. This data will already exist on the type specimen Wikidata item. See for example

https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Asaphodes_ida_%28Clarke,_1926%29_%28AM_AMNZ2182_3-1%29.jpg and the related type specimen Wikidata item <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q136936057>.

If the image file depicts a specimen that is **NOT** a type specimen then it is recommended the properties related to data about the physical object should be used to add structured data to the specimen image file.

Referencing of structured data statements

It is recommended that any statements added to a specimen image file, whether about the file itself or about the specimen depicted in that file, should be referenced giving the source of data represented in that statement. It is also recommended that a retrieved date be added to clarify when that data was sourced and added to the image file.

File name and caption

Holotype specimen image file name

It is recommended that if the specimen image is a holotype specimen the file name should be formatted as follows:

Holotype of [species name] ([inventory number]).jpg

Darwin Core Equivalency: [dwc:identification](#)
 [dwc:catalogNumber](#)

Holotype specimen image file caption

It is recommended the caption for a holotype specimen image file be formatted as follows:

Holotype specimen of [species name] ([Inventory number]) held at [holding collection].

Non type specimen image

It is recommended for those images of specimens that are NOT type specimens, the file name given is formatted as follows:

[species name] ([inventory number]).jpg

Darwin Core Equivalency: [dwc:identification](#)
 [dwc:catalogNumber](#)

Non type specimen image file caption

It is recommended the caption for a specimen image file be formatted as follows:

Specimen of [species name] ([inventory number]) held at [holding collection].

Note the above recommendations were decided after many of the example files had already been uploaded into Wikimedia Commons and therefore are intended to apply to future uploads of specimen images only.

Wikidata properties for file SDC

Depicts

The purpose of depicts statements is to provide machine-readable, multilingual descriptions of what is visible in a particular image file, making it **easier to search and find content** across different languages in Wikimedia Commons. For further information see

https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Commons:Structured_data/Modeling/Depiction.

Debate exists amongst the Wikimedia Commons community on the extent and specificity of depicts statements attached to image files. This data model encourages editors to add multiple depicts statements - where appropriate - to achieve the aspirations outlined above. Unlike an art object, a natural history specimen and its image may relate to several taxonomic concepts. By encouraging the creation of several “depicts” statements, this data model aims to ensure the structured data attached to those files can be easily queried thus helping to improve the findability of specimen image files by the varied communities that may wish to access and reuse those images.

Items portrayed in this file

[Edit](#)
[depicts](#)

Search to add items	from Wikidata	...
Asaphodes ida		Mark as prominent
Reference		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> reference URL: https://www.aucklandmuseum.com/collection/object/am_naturalsciences-object-181379 retrieved: 3 February 2026 		
Xanthorhoe ida		Mark as prominent
Reference		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> reference URL: https://www.aucklandmuseum.com/collection/object/am_naturalsciences-object-181379 retrieved: 3 February 2026 		
holotype of Asaphodes ida		Mark as prominent
Reference		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> reference URL: https://www.aucklandmuseum.com/collection/object/am_naturalsciences-object-181379 retrieved: 3 February 2026 		
holotype		Mark as prominent
Reference		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> reference URL: https://www.aucklandmuseum.com/collection/object/am_naturalsciences-object-181379 retrieved: 3 February 2026 		

Screenshot of the structured data tab of a [Wikimedia Commons specimen image file](#) showing multiple depicts statements. Wikimedia Foundation. [CC BY-SA 4.0](#).

This data model recognises that currently many of those searching for natural history specimen images on Wikimedia Commons will use the default search engine [Media Search](#). Media Search uses the depicts statements contained in the structured data attached to the file, as well as Wikimedia Commons categories and Wikitext, to inform its search result. This data model therefore follows the advice given in [Help:Media Search](#) which recommends adding all the depicts statements that are appropriate to describe what the file represents.

[Depicts](#) (P180) Wikidata item for the currently accepted valid **taxonomic name** of species

If possible the Wikidata item for the currently accepted and valid taxonomic name for the species should be added to the SDC. Qualifiers to this statement are unnecessary as the data about the taxon should be on the taxon Wikidata item.

Example:

https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Asaphodes_ida_%28Clarke,_1926%29_%28AM_AMNZ21823-1%29.jpg

Darwin Core equivalence: [dwc:scientificName](#) Taxonomic name of species
[dwc:acceptedNameUsage](#) Accepted taxonomic name

[Depicts](#) (P180) Wikidata item for the taxonomic name of the species given in file metadata or title.

This may be different from the current name and may possibly be a taxonomic synonym. If a Wikidata item for this taxon name does not yet exist the recommended that a Wikidata item be created. Qualifiers to this statement are unnecessary as the data about the taxon name (including its taxonomic status) should be on the taxon Wikidata item.

Darwin Core equivalence: [dwc:scientificName](#) Taxonomic name of species

Example:

https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Asaphodes_ida_%28Clarke,_1926%29_%28AM_AMNZ21823-1%29.jpg

Darwin Core equivalence: [dwc:scientificName](#) Taxonomic name given in file metadata or title

[Depicts](#) (P180) [holotype](#) (Q1061403), [syntype](#) (Q719822), [paratype](#) (Q926578) [lectotype](#) (Q2439719), [paralectotype](#) (Q19353473), [neotype](#) (Q3874702), [allotype](#) (Q19353437)

To be added if the image is depicting a type specimen. This statement facilitates the use of the more basic Wikidata query builder to assist in creating a SPARQL query to find appropriate type specimen images via the Wikimedia Commons query service.

Darwin Core equivalence: [dwc:type](#) Type status of specimen

Example:

https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Asaphodes_ida_%28Clarke,_1926%29_%28AM_AMNZ21823-1%29.jpg

[Depicts](#) (P180) Wikidata item for type specimen.

This data is to be added if the type specimen has a Wikidata item created for it.

Darwin core equivalence: [dwc:identificationID](#) Wikidata QID for type specimen

Example:

[https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Asaphodes_ida_\(Clarke,_1926\)_ \(AM_AMNZ21823-1\).jpg](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Asaphodes_ida_(Clarke,_1926)_ (AM_AMNZ21823-1).jpg)

Copyright status

[Copyright status](#) (P6216) [copyrighted](#) (Q50423863), [public domain](#) (Q19652), [no known copyright](#) (Q47530955), [copyrighted, dedicated to the public domain by copyright holder](#) (Q88088423)

If in the public domain the following qualifier is recommended

[applies to jurisdiction](#) (P1001) → Wikidata item for copyright jurisdiction. [recommended]

Example: https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Allodiscus_turbotti_MA70898_002.jpg

Copyright license

[Copyright licence](#) (P275) Wikidata item for the copyright licence used to release the image for reuse.

Example: https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Allodiscus_turbotti_MA70898_002.jpg

Dublin Core equivalence: [dcterms:licence](#)

Inception (of digital object)

[Inception](#) (P571) date of the creation of the digital image
 [applies to part](#) (P518) → [digital object](#) (Q59138870) [optional]

Example:

https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Asaphodes_ida_%28Clarke,_1926%29_%28AM_AMNZ21823-1%29.jpg

Dublin Core equivalence: [dcterms:created](#)

Collection

[Collection](#) (P195) Wikidata item for collection (see [GRSciColl](#)) -
 [object of statement has role](#) (P3831) → [holding collection](#) (Q137935182) [recommended]

[Collection](#) (P195) Wikidata item for parent institution of collection
 [object of statement has role](#) (P3831) → [holding institution](#) (Q131597993) [recommended]

These statements relate to both the collection that holds both the image file and the specimen and the parent institution of that collection. Two statements are recommended where the holding collection and the holding institution differs. An example would be the Auckland War Memorial Museum herbarium and the Auckland War Memorial Museum itself.

The current conventional use of “collection” within Wikimedia Commons templates and in the wider GLAM community of Wikimedia Commons is synonymous with an institution. See for example the [art work template](#) where the [institution template](#) would be applied to the “collection” field. However in natural history, the term “collection” refers to the various scientific collections held by the parent institution. This data model ensures more specificity and gives broader querying capabilities when searching for natural history collections, while still honouring the conventional use of the term collection in Wikimedia Commons. This portion of the model ensures community needs are satisfied through the addition of two statements but also ensures, via the qualifiers, that the two statements can be distinguished.

Example: https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Brachyglottis_huntii_%28CHR_602367%29.jpg

Darwin Core equivalency: [dwc:collectionID](#) Wikidata item for collection

Instance of

[Instance of](#) (P31) [photograph](#) (Q125191)
[video recording](#) (Q34508)
[Xray](#) (Q34777)
[audio file](#) (Q26987229)

Example: https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Brachyglottis_huntii_%28CHR_602367%29.jpg

Darwin Core equivalence: [dwc:type](#) Wikidata item for type of file

Creator

[Creator](#) (P170) Wikidata item for the creator of the digital image.

This can be an institution or an employee of an institution or a separate individual. If it is an employee acting on behalf of an institution, the institution should also be added.

Example:
https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Mecodema_haunoho_Holotype_NZAC04067064.png

Dublin core equivalence: [dcterms:creator](#)

Sponsor

[Sponsor](#) (P859) Wikidata item for sponsor of the digitisation
[object of statement has role](#) (P3831) → [digitization sponsor](#) (Q131344184) [recommended]

Example:
https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Asaphodes_ida_%28Clarke_1926%29_%28AM_AMNZ21823-1%29.jpg

Copyright holder

[Copyright holder](#) (P3931) Wikidata item for the institution or individual that holds the copyright of the image.

For further information see
https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Commons:Structured_data/Modeling/Copyright

Example:
https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Odontria_cassinae_Given_1952_NZAC04067248.jpg

Dublin Core equivalence: [dcterms:rightsHolder](#)

Source of file

[Source of file](#) (P7482) [file available on the internet](#) (Q74228490) The direct source of the file uploaded to Commons

[operator](#) (P137) → Wikidata item for the institution that is the source of the file [recommended]
[described at URL](#) (P973) → Add url of the source of the file (normally an institutions website) [recommended]

If the same image can be sourced from a variety of sources all these may be added to the structured data of the image file. However the source of the image file for the upload into Wikicommons should be made prominent.

Example:

https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Mecodema_haunoho_Holotype_NZAC04067064.png

Dublin Core equivalence: [dcterms:source](#)

Wikidata properties for specimen SDC

The below statements should only be added to non type specimen images. If the image file relates to a type specimen, the below statements should be added to that specimen's Wikidata item and be linked to the Wikimedia Commons image file via a depicts statement relating to that type specimen Wikidata item.

It is recommended that any of the below statements be referenced with a link to the URL for the record in the providing institutions database. It is also recommended that a retrieved date be added to ensure future editors are aware of when the data was sourced and added.

Inventory number

[Inventory number](#) (P217) institution inventory number (ideally the persistent identifier for the object depicted as created by the institution that holds the collection)
[applies to part](#) (P518) → [physical object](#) (Q223557) [recommended]
[collection](#) (P195) → Wikidata item for the collection the inventory number is sourced from [recommended]

It is recommended that, where possible, this statement be referenced with a link to URL for the record in the providing institutions database as well as the date at which that URL was retrieved.

Example: https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Brachyglottis_huntii_%28CHR_602367%29.jpg

Darwin Core equivalency: [dwc:catalogNumber](#) institution inventory number
[dwc:institutionID](#) collection the inventory number is sourced from

Date of collection of specimen

[Collection date](#) (P14027) date of collection of specimen
[applies to part](#) (P518) → [physical object](#) (Q223557) [recommended]

Example: https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Brachyglottis_huntii_%28CHR_602367%29.jpg

Darwin Core Equivalency: [dwc:eventDate](#) date of collection of specimen

Collector (of physical object)

[Collector](#) (P13914) Wikidata item for the collector of specimen
[applies to part](#) (P518) → [physical object](#) (Q223557) [recommended]

Example: https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Anisoplaca_achyrota_NZAC04201756.jpg

Darwin Core equivalency: [dwc:recordedByID](#) Wikidata item for the specimen collector

Specimen classifier

[Specimen classifier](#) (P14026) Wikidata item the determiner of the specimen
[applies to part](#) (P518) → [physical object](#) (Q223557) [recommended]
[point in time](#) (P585) → date of determination

Example: https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Brachyglottis_huntii_%28CHR_602367%29.jpg

Darwin Core equivalency: [dwc:identifiedbyID](#) Wikidata item for the determiner of the specimen
[dwc:dateIdentified](#) Date of determination

Location collected

[Location collected](#) (P14117) Wikidata item for location collected
Applies to part (P518) → [physical object](#) (Q223557) [recommended]

Example: https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Anisoplaca_achyrota_NZAC04201756.jpg

Darwin Core equivalency: [dwc:verbatimLocality](#)

Coordinates for location collected

[Coordinate location](#) (P625) Text string of the latitude and longitude coordinates for the location where the specimen depicted was collected.

Applies to part (P518) → [physical object](#) (Q223557) [recommended]

Object of statement has role → [location collected](#) (Q138018332) [recommended]

Example: https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Brachyglottis_huntii_%28CHR_602367%29.jpg

Darwin Core equivalency:

[dwc:decimalLatitude](#)

[dwc:decimalLongitude](#)

Sex (of depicted physical object)

[Sex or gender](#) (P21) [Female organism](#) (Q43445) [Male organism](#) (Q44148)

[Hermaphrodite](#) (Q303479)

[applies to part](#) (P518) → [physical object](#) (Q223557) [recommended]

Example: https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Antiscopa_acompa_NZAC04201771.jpg

Darwin Core equivalency: [dwc:sex](#) Wikidata item for sex of specimen

Significant event

[Significant event](#) (P793) Wikidata item for significant event.

[applies to part](#) (P518) → [physical object](#) (Q223557) [recommended]

Particularly relevant for [research expedition](#) (Q366301) See [Wikidata:WikiProject Research expeditions](#).

Example: https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Digitaria_setigera_CHR_77607.png

Darwin Core equivalency: [dwc:eventID](#) Wikidata item for significant event

Example images

https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Anisoplaca_achyrotia_NZAC04201756.jpg NZAC specimen image

https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Cryptasasma_querula_NZAC04201699.jpg NZAC specimen image

https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Asaphodes_ida_%28Clarke,_1926%29_%28AM_AMNZ21823-1%29.jpg Auckland Museum holotype image

https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Mecodema_haunoho_Holotype_NZAC04067064.png New Zealand Arthropod Collection holotype image

https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Allodiscus_turbotti_MA70898_002.jpg Auckland Museum holotype specimen image

https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Odontria_cassiniae_Given,_1952_NZAC04067248.jpg New Zealand Arthropod Collection holotype image

https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Brachyglottis_huntii_%28CHR_602367%29.jpg Allan Herbarium specimen image

https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Antiscopa_acompa_NZAC04201771.jpg NZAC specimen image

https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Digitaria_setigera_CHR_77607.png Allan Herbarium specimen image

https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Mycomya_quadrimaculata_-_Steve_Kerr_-_170022015.jpeg Holotype specimen image sourced from iNaturalist

Model interlinking

Below is an example of files and items that illustrate the interlinked Structured Data on Commons specimen image model, Biodiversity Heritage Library Structured Data on Commons illustration model and the holotype specimen Wikidata item data model.

Holotype specimen image

[https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Preserved_colours_of_Haplochromis_argens_male_holotype_\(RMNH.PISC.83588\)_-_ZooKeys-256-001-g005.jpeg](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Preserved_colours_of_Haplochromis_argens_male_holotype_(RMNH.PISC.83588)_-_ZooKeys-256-001-g005.jpeg)

Holotype specimen illustration

https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Haplochromis_argens_male_holotype,_RMNH.PISC.83588_-_ZooKeys-256-001-g002.jpg

Holotype specimen Wikidata item

<https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q137830487>

Species taxon Wikidata item

Haplochromis argens <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q5455779>

Species English Wikipedia page

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Haplochromis_argens

Example queries of the Wikimedia Commons Query Service

The Wikimedia Commons query service can be located here

<https://commons-query.wikimedia.org/>

<https://w.wiki/HicR> Query showing all Wikimedia Commons files with structured data statements instance of photograph and depicts *Asaphodes ida*

<https://w.wiki/HicY> Query showing all Wikimedia Commons files with structured data statements instance of photograph, depicts holotype, collection New Zealand Arthropod Collection

<https://w.wiki/HifF> Query showing photographs where the collector is Sean P. Clancy and the collection is the New Zealand Arthropod Collection

Other related links

[WikiProject Natural History specimen data model link](#)

[Crosswalk for Darwin Core and SDC data model link](#)

[Wikidata & Wikimedia Commons as Platforms for Scientific Knowledge](#)

[Data model natural history type specimen Wikidata items](#)

[BHL SDC data model for BHL illustrations](#)

[Template:Specimen](#)

[Template:Biohis](#)

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